

THE HISTORY OF THE FORMATION OF JAZZ ART AND THE PLACE OF LOUIS ARMSTRONG IN IT

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Abstract: *The article focuses on the commonalities formed in the creative and performance features of the formation of jazz art. In particular, the musical phrases, forms, and instruments widely used in jazz music performance traditions are discussed, as well as their musical importance in all nations.*

Keywords: *composer, jazz, piano, genre.*

Jazz (in English jazz) is a kind of musical art developed under the influence of African rhythms, European harmony, with the participation of elements of African American and Latin American folklore.

Jazz as a phenomenon originated in the southern United States in the late 19th and early 20th centuries and quickly spread to all developed countries. As a multicultural phenomenon, jazz is enriched with various regional musical characteristics. The development of jazz was also influenced by marching bands in the streets of US cities on holidays, as well as military and dance bands. By the 1920s, popular music and jazz had become almost synonymous for many, with American critics contrasting it primarily with the US commercial music industry.

Constantly changing and passing through several characteristic stages of development, jazz rose to the level of high art. In the 1920s-1940s, large jazz orchestras consisting of 20-40 musicians performed swing dances.

Experimental, improvisational jazz and be-bop were developed in small ensembles. The modern meaning of this term appeared in the 1950s, when jazz of various currents was combined into a musical genre, with a description that combined different styles of all eras. Most varieties of the genre are characterized by swing, vocal expression, improvisation, reliance on riffs, use of frets with blues notes.

Gradually, jazz approached the realm of high art, maintaining the contrasting identity of both popular and academic music. Jazz remains influential and is supported by academia, foundation funds and a worldwide network of festivals. Jazz's legacy is widely recognized and continues to influence world music culture.

The word "jazz" (its variations: "jas", "jass", "jascz", "jasz", "jaz") appeared as a West Coast slang term around the 1910s. The term "jazz" was first applied to music in Chicago in 1915. In his works, jazz historian Lawrence Gashi Noting that it did not originate in New Orleans, and that early jazz musicians did not use it, they added the same improvisational elements to their music and called it "their own version of ragtime." - moved there only after it was actively used in the north (in the sense of Chicago) in 1958, and since 1958 William Hogan at Tulane University archives of hundreds of interviews with jazz musicians born in New Orleans between 1885 and 1901. In 2000, the American Dialect Society named the word "jazz" the word of the 20th century.

One of the first jazz musicians, Garvin Bushell, was convinced that the origin of the word "jazz" belonged to the perfume industry. In his 1988 book, *Jazz From the Beginning*, he recalled his early years in music: "The perfume industry in New Orleans was huge in those days because the French brought it (from the old world). They used jasmine oil in all the scents to give strength and energy. So when something was a little 'dead,' they said, 'Let's jazz it up a little.'" Notably, a similar phrase was later used in baseball. In the 1920s, John Phillips Sousa suggested that "jazz" entered the American lexicon through vaudeville, where all the actors returned to the stage at the end of the show to give a fiery and noisy finale called "jazzbo". is a word, because it consists of 2 roots - "jazz" and "rich", and apparently was an abbreviation of the word "rich" (from English - "rich").

Etymologists have also pointed to Jasper, a dancing slave, who worked on plantations near New Orleans in the early 19th century, nicknamed "Jazz", a Mississippi drummer named Chas Washington in the late 19th century, alias Ray Charles Alexander in the early 20th century. , Chicago musician Jasbo Brown, New

Orleans orchestra conductor Mr. Razz (Eng. Mr. Razz), French "chasse" (French chasse) is a floating dance step, in the 1830s the American archetypal verb "sashay" (from English - "o 'tooth'), became another French word 'jaser', which means 'to talk useless for the pleasure of hearing one's voice', or Arabic means "charm". It means "promiscuous". Jazz's close association with African-American culture has led others to look to African languages for its origins: in Mandinka, "jasi" means "different from oneself," while in Luba, "jaja" is interpreted as "a reason to dance." , or Dark "yas" means "to be extraordinarily alive or vigorous."

"Jazz" is supposed to be derived from the obsolete word "jasm", which in turn is derived from "jism" or "gism". The historical dictionary of American Slang in 1860 interpreted "body" as "spirit", "energy" or "force", and the same meaning with the appearance of the word "gism" in the Oxford English Dictionary in 1842 - also applies to the year. Etymologist Gerald Cohen, a leading researcher on the origin of the word "jazz", believes that the words "gism" and "jasm" are not related to each other, and they can be completely independent. "Jism" or its variant "jizz" (not attested in the Historical Dictionary of American Slang until 1941) has also been suggested as a direct source of "jazz". A direct derivation from "body" is phonologically unlikely.

According to this assumption, the word "body" is an intermediate form. The connection between the words "jazm" and "jazz" is confirmed by an article in the Daily Californian of February 18, 1916, which uses the spelling "jaz-m", which, based on the context and other publications of the time, refers to the musical genre held Josiah Holland's Miss Gilbert's Career: An American Story defines the word "body."

As you can see, at that time this word was new and had not yet taken its place in people's speech. According to other versions, "jazz" originated among white Americans, and the first printed use of the word was in the field of baseball in California (San Francisco Evening News[en]) in the 1910s, when it was described as "lively ", meaning "strong". , "community spirit" ("Let's jazz this up!" - from English - "let's liven up / cheer up!"). The earliest known usage appears in an article dated April 2, 1912, found by researcher George Thompson in 2003 in the digital archives of The

New York Times. Los Angeles Angels pitcher Ben Henderson talked about a new type of throw called the jazz curve: "This year I learned a new type of throw. I call it the 'Jazz Ball' because the ball is it swings that way, you can't do anything about it." baseball was described as "energetic and invigorating" and it was simply played and had no official name. said that he learned about this term from his colleague Spike Slattery (English. William (Spike) Slattery) in a training camp in 1913 team[19].

It is safe to say that this word was new at the time, because on March 6, 1913, Scoop decided to clarify its meaning. Spike heard the phrase from the performers at one of the craps shows, who yelled, "Come on, old jazz." Art Hickman, a local musician who was unemployed at the time, took over the camp's evening entertainment. Among them was a ragtime band he co-founded with other off-duty musicians, including a banjo player. It was this group that founded a new sound, later called jazz in the camp. By the following year, the term had made its way to Chicago, possibly through the efforts of another group leader, Bert Kelly. In 1916, it appeared there under a different spelling as the New Orleans Jazz Band. Despite the group's name, the word was not used in New Orleans until 1917, as early jazz musicians testify.

On April 5, 1913, the same newspaper (San Francisco Evening Herald) published a large article by Ernest Hopkins about the meaning and spelling of the word "jazz". As the Oxford English Dictionary points out, it was clearly a novelty: "The existence of an article entitled 'In Praise of Jazz: A Futuristic Newcomer' about the new word suggests that it was new at the time." ". The Oxford English Dictionary once noted that the word "jazz" was documented in 1909, three years before it was mentioned in baseball. But it was a mistake - they mixed up two recordings of the same comedy monologue written by the same artist Cal Stewart. In 1909, he created a record called "Uncle Josh in Society." The word "jazz" is not used here. He introduced the same notation in 1919 and added the word "jazz" because by then it had become popular.

Over time, this term was absorbed into other languages. For example, in Spanish, the spelling remains the same, but the pronunciation changes and varies by dialect—Chileans pronounce it "yas" (English yass, pronounced: /ja:s/), while Argentines

pronounce it this way. In Russian, the pronunciation is similar, but the term is transliterated as "jaz" in the Cyrillic alphabet.

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